

Adamas as diamond and its occurrence near Ancient Philippi in Macedonia, northern Greece

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(Received: 22 May 2023; accepted in revised form: 10 July 2023)

Abstract. The adamas of Ancient peoples is proved to be the precious diamond. An ancient and unconventional diamond occurrence, the mines of Philippi in Macedonia (northern Greece), is geologically explained here. The most probable source is believed to be flat subduction-related (shoshonitic) lamprophyres that originated at a depth of >110 km within the mantle in the diamond stability field. The thick lithospheric mantle beneath Greece supports the occurrence of diamondiferous lamprophyric rocks in this area. However, no lamprophyre outcrops have been found, except for a few lamprophyre dikes 14 km SE of Philippi. Another explanation for the occurrence would implicate detrital diamonds that have been preserved in the local greenschist facies rocks. The XRD analysis of Philippi paragneiss showed the existence of the mantle mineral magnesioiwüstite, which is a possible diamond indicator. The Philippi occurrence deserves detailed investigation involving alluvial sampling and ground magnetic surveys to locate the diamond source.

Kamvisis, I., Chandra Phani, P.R. 2023. Adamas as diamond and its occurrence near Ancient Philippi in Macedonia, northern Greece. *Geologica Balcanica* 52 (2), 83–88.

Keywords: adamas, diamond, Philippi, subduction, lamprophyres, paragneiss.

INTRODUCTION

The ancient Greeks and Romans called the most precious of stones “adamas.” The word diamond is derived from the Greek word “adamas,” which means untamed. It is the hardest of gemstones with a hardness of 10 in the Mohs scale. Diamonds were first discovered in India around 800 B.C. where they are still being mined for almost three millennia (e.g., Phani, 2019). Except for India, the main source of diamonds in antiquity, there were a few other minor localities. One of them was Ancient Philippi. The present work is important as it proves that the ancient adamas is actually diamond. Europe’s first diamond occurrence, the Philippi gold mine, was used as a case study. This area belongs geotectonically to the

Lower Rhodope Unit (known as the Pirin-Pangaion Unit). It is composed mostly of Paleozoic marbles, which have been intruded by the 30 Ma Philippi pluton (Tranos *et al.*, 2009, Fig. 1). There are also intrusion-related ores in the area.

DISCUSSION

Pliny the Elder wrote in *Natural History* “[...] engravers, who enclose them [the adamas particles] in iron, are enabled thereby, with the greatest facility, to cut the very hardest substances known.” Ancient peoples didn’t confuse diamond with hard but softer minerals, in particular natural platinum alloys like rutheniridosmine (Mohs scale 6–7), quartz (Mohs

Fig. 1. a) Geological map of the area (modified from Tranos *et al.*, 2009). 1 – Recent sediments; 2 – Philippi pluton; 3 – Marble and schist; 4 – Schist; 5 – Paragneiss; 6 – Marble; 7 – Foliation; 8 – Form-strike lines. The white diamond is the position of Ancient Philippi. b) Dark monzodiorite from the Philippi mafic pluton.

Fig. 2. a) An ancient Greek sapphire and diamond ring from around 300 B.C. (photo by O. Bopearachchi); b) the Vallerano diamond ring in the National Roman Museum from 150–180 A.D. (photo from Bedini *et al.*, 2012); c–f) 3rd century A.D. Roman diamond rings from the British Museum; g) 3rd–4th century A.D. Roman diamond ring from the Metropolitan Museum; h) 3rd century A.D. roman ring with two diamonds from the British Museum; i) Roman ring with diamond and emerald from the Thorvaldsen Museum; j) Roman diamond and garnet seal from the Castellani Collection (photo from Ogden, 2018).

scale 7), Herkimer-type “diamond” (Mohs scale 7–7.5), the common abrasive emery from the Greek island of Naxos (Mohs scale 8) or adamantine spar (a rare clear brown but silky corundum, Mohs scale 9). This is confirmed by the discovery by archeologists of ancient Greek and Roman diamond jewelry (mostly rings and a garnet and diamond seal, see Fig. 2).

Pliny also stated in his *Natural History* “[...] another one [adamas], which was found in the gold mines at Philippi, is known as the Macedonian adamas: the latter is about as large as a cucumber seed”. That would be ~5 mm across or 0.5 ct. The

diamonds had a silvery gray color. Regarding the position of the Philippi mines in the Roman era, Appian wrote in *Civil Wars* that “there is another hill not far from Philippi, which is called the Hill of Dionysus, where there are gold mines called the Asyla.” In 1926, the renowned archeologist S. Casson distinguished the gold sources: those of Mt. Pangaion were separate from the new strike near Philippi on the Hill of Dionysus. The hill, according to Appian, was in a distance of 8 stades (~1262 m) W of Ancient Philippi and 10 stades (~1577 m) from two granitoid hillocks in the plain. The mines were probably located in the Philippi

plain since there is a “bull’s eye” magnetic anomaly appearing under the 2000-year-old alluvium and the nearby hills (Stampolidis *et al.*, 2000; see Fig. 3). Macrodiamonds have been known to be associated with “headless placers” in gold panning areas like Borneo, the Urals, California, NSW, Burma and Thailand (Davies *et al.*, 2002), but also in Ireland, Victoria (Birch and Barron, 1997), Tasmania (Bottrill, 1998), the Appalachians (Hausel, 1998), Siberia (Afanas’ev *et al.*, 2011), North Algeria (Godard *et al.*, 2014) and Sumatra (Van Gorsel, 2018). No kimberlites, orangeites and anorogenic olivine lamproites have been found in these areas. An unconventional diamond source has been suggested.

One possible model for the genesis of diamonds near Ancient Philippi is through flat subduction (Wyman *et al.*, 2016). The diamonds formed at the subducted slab would then be picked up and transported to the surface by rapidly ascending lamprophyric magmas, which could be generated at depths of up to 250 km or even 300 km within the mantle (Smith *et al.*, 2016; Smit *et al.*, 2022). The lithosphere under Greece is exceptionally deep, comprising the thick oceanic lithosphere and a portion of the Hellenic subducting slab (see Artemieva *et al.*, 2006; Sodoudi *et al.*, 2006; Celli *et al.*, 2020; see Fig. 4). This is within the diamond stability field (*i.e.*, >110 km depth, see Stachel and Luth, 2015).

Fig. 3. Total field anomalies W of Philippi. The right anomaly is reduced to the N (after Stampolidis *et al.*, 2000).

Fig. 4. Lithospheric thickness under the African plate and nearby areas (Greece is in the Eastern Mediterranean). Red dots are kimberlites (after Celli *et al.*, 2020).

Fig. 5. a, b) Lamprophyre dikes from the broader area. a) photo by Fornadel *et al.* (2021); b) photo by Voudouris *et al.* (2016).

Worldwide, there are several diamondiferous calc-alkaline lamprophyre locations, such as Lake Gibson in Canada (McRae *et al.*, 1996), Wawa in Canada (Lefebvre, 2004), Kizil-Kum in Uzbekistan (Kaminsky, 2007) and Dachine in Guyana (Smith *et al.*, 2012). The major problem in the study area is that there are no lamprophyres found in its vicinity. Lamprophyres are found 14 km to the southeast of Philippi near Kavala (see Fig. 5) and possibly 22 km to the south, near the Nea Peramos camp. The lack of lamprophyre dikes on the surface could be explained if these are covered by scree and vegetation on the hills or alluvium in the plain. It should be noted, however, that there is a plethora of pillow-like mafic microgranular enclaves (MME) in the pluton confirming an even more substantial mafic magma input from the mantle (Eleftheriadis *et al.*, 1995). By focusing on the geochemistry, one can see certain similarities between the Canadian dia-

mondiferous lamprophyres (the large Akluilâk dike in Lake Gibson and Wawa) and the Greek rocks (Kavala lamprophyre, Philippi MME) such as their MgO content (see Table 1).

Another plausible model for these diamonds would implicate detrital diamonds preserved in greenschist-facies metasediments (W. Griffin, pers. comm.). There are examples around the world like the Akwatia metagraywackes-metapelites in Ghana (Asiedu *et al.*, 2004), the Wawa metaconglomerates in Canada (Kopylova *et al.*, 2011) and the Dachine metaconglomerates in Guyana (Bassoo *et al.*, 2021). The study area includes greenschist-facies paragneiss. A paragneiss sample (coordinates 41°04'54.0"N; 24°20'09.4"E) was analyzed by XRD. The 3350 recorded values were processed with the Match!3 Program. The results confirmed the presence of the mantle mineral magnesio-wüstite (see Fig. 6). The original sediments must

Table 1

Major oxides: Akluilâk lamprophyre 325D (McRae *et al.*, 1996), Wawa lamprophyre NL-37 (Lefebvre, 2004), Kavala lamprophyre GL22 (Kamvisis and Vasyukova, 2021) and Philippi MME YD8 (Eleftheriadis *et al.*, 1995)

Sample →	325D	NL-37	GL22	YD8
SiO ₂	43.49	58.96	54.70	51.93
TiO ₂	1.08	0.71	0.69	0.87
Al ₂ O ₃	14.88	13.80	15.90	16.61
Fe ₂ O _{3T}	7.01	8.79	7.12	9.12
MnO	0.27	0.11	0.15	0.36
MgO	4.71	5.32	5.35	4.73
CaO	8.88	6.38	6.25	8.30
Na ₂ O	0.73	3.59	3.58	4.23
K ₂ O	9.53	0.78	2.61	1.85

Fig. 6. XRD results from a paragneiss NE of Philippi. Magnesio-wüstite is also included.

have originated from the weathering of a non-kimberlitic source due to lack of diamond indicators (e.g., G10 garnet, Cr-diopside, magnesiochromite, microilmelite).

CONCLUSIONS

The adamas of the Ancient peoples has been proved to be diamond. The Ancient Philippi mining area occurrence in Greece, presented in this article, is geologically explained. The diamonds could have formed during flat subduction and carried up by shoshonitic lamprophyres. A different formation model would include detrital diamonds preserved

in greenschist-facies metasediments. An XRD analysis took place for paragneiss, confirming the existence of a diamond indicator, magnesiowüstite. Diamond exploration (alluvial sampling, ground magnetic survey) is necessary for understanding this unconventional occurrence.

Acknowledgements

We thank P. Arkai, L. Barron, G. Christofides, W. Griffin, F. Kaminsky, P. Keating, A. Photiades, G. Pe-Piper, H. Putz, T. Stachel, E. Vasyukova, P. Voudouris, I. Zananiri and the two anonymous reviewers for their help and useful suggestions. The study was self-funded.

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